

Female Labour Force Participation in Asia : A Literature Review

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Abstract

The active participation of working-age women in productive economic activities is known as female labour force participation. It has been recognised as an important measure of gender equality, women's empowerment, and sustainable economic growth. This study examines the factors influencing female labour force participation in South Asia. This study aims to examine the persistent paradox: sustained economic growth, rising female educational attainment, and declining fertility rates in the South Asia region, but the women's labour market participation in the region is the lowest in the world, about 33 per cent in 2025, compared to a global average of 48.9 per cent (World Bank, 2025). The study found that only economic growth does not increase women's participation; the composition of growth is more important than the aggregate rate, and that there is a U-shaped relationship between education and participation. Demand-side factors, especially 'jobless growth' led by capital-intensive structural transformation, are the main drivers of the low female labour force participation rate in India. Social norms constrain women's labour-market participation at all income and educational levels. Improving the economic participation of women in South Asia needs a mix of supply-side and demand-side interventions, including targeted industrial policy, childcare provision, technical and vocational training, and sustained norm change initiatives.

Keywords

Female Labour Force Participation; South Asia; Feminisation U-Hypothesis.

Introduction

The ILO standard definition of the labour force participation rate used here is: the proportion of the working-age population that is either employed or actively seeking employment (ILO, 2023).

Women's economic participation has been an important area of development economics. Understanding why women work and what factors influence their entry into the labour force has direct consequences for household welfare, national productivity, and the achievement of sustainable goals. In recent decades, many researchers have studied how economic development affects women's labour market participation, following Goldin's (1995) U-shaped relationship between economic development and female labour force participation. Goldin observed that women's market work declines in the early stages of industrialisation, then rises again at higher levels of development, as the composition of available jobs shifts from manual to white-collar occupations.

The literature on female labour force participation broadly divides into two approaches. The supply-side approach focuses on individual and household characteristics, including education, marital status, fertility, household income, and social norms, which impact a woman's decision to enter the labour market. The demand-side approach indicates structural economic factors, including sectoral employment patterns, composition of structural transformation, and the availability of jobs suited to female workers. Both approaches are important to understanding South Asia.

South Asia includes India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Nepal, Afghanistan, Bhutan, and the Maldives. The region is home to nearly two billion people and has experienced rapid economic growth, improvements in female education, and declining fertility rates. Still, female labour force participation remains among the lowest in the world. According to ILO modelled estimates, the female labour force participation rate in South Asia stood at 33 per cent in 2025, compared with 77.4 per cent for men, a gender gap of 44 percentage points or more. This gap is wider than the global average, where female participation was 48.9 per cent compared to 73.1 per cent for men (World Bank, 2025).

This study reviews the studies organised into five main themes discussed in the female labour force participation literature (1) economic development and the feminisation U-hypothesis, (2) education and FLFP, (3) sectoral composition and structural transformation, (4) marriage, fertility, and care responsibilities, (5) social and cultural norms.

Objective of study

The study aims to examine the recent studies in determinants of women's labour force participation in South Asia and to propose policy measures that address both supply-side and demand-side constraints

Review of Literature

Economic Development and the Feminisation U-Hypothesis

Goldin's (1995) feminisation U-hypothesis predicts that female labour force participation follows a U-shaped path: participation is high in agrarian economies, decreases during the industrialisation, and recovers when the economy generates white-collar service and manufacturing jobs that attract female workers. This hypothesis has been the main theoretical reference in the FLFP literature, but has not been consistently found in South Asian countries, including India. Lahoti and Swaminathan (2016) find no evidence of a systematic U-shaped relationship between state domestic product and Female labour force participation in India. Their key findings showed that the composition of growth matters more than its aggregate level. Expansion in agricultural and construction employment is positively associated with female participation, but the manufacturing growth is not. Klasen (2019) also concludes that Female labour force participation trends in South Asia and the Middle East do not support the U-shaped hypothesis. Women's economic participation has been declining, not recovering, despite income growth. Taken together, these two studies show that the U-hypothesis may describe a general tendency in Western development rather than a universal law. For South Asia, aggregate economic growth is not an automatic mechanism for raising women's participation.

Education and Female Labour Force Participation

A second major area of the literature examines how education affects women's economic participation. The neoclassical expectation of Human Capital Theory by Becker (1964) is that more education raises women's market wages and that incentivises them to work. However, in South Asia, the relationship is more complex and nonlinear. U-shaped pattern between educational attainment and labour force participation, in which women with secondary education have lower participation rates than primary-educated and tertiary-educated women.

The U-shaped relationship has been confirmed across different studies. Najeeb et al. (2020) and Kanjilal-Bhaduri & Pastore (2018) find that while tertiary education significantly increases participation, secondary education often reduces it relative to primary levels. Klasen and Pieters' (2015) study of married urban Indian women finds that lower women's participation in the economy is due to the income effect: higher household income, often driven by husbands' education and higher income, reduces women's need to work. Seneviratne (2019), also drawing on the Sri Lankan context, shows that Secondary-educated married women do not opt for low-skilled work because of the social stigma attached to it, which reduces their participation. Chen et al. (2021) show that rising education has not been matched by adequate labour market demand, which is limiting the translation of human capital gains into actual workforce participation. In these studies, a clear pattern emerges: secondary education raises women's expected wages but does not lead to access to appropriate formal employment. The education-participation paradox shows a structural mismatch between the supply of educated women and the demand for their skills in labour markets that are dominated by informal, low-skilled, or male-dominated occupations.

Sectoral Composition and Structural Transformation

A third area of literature examines how the composition of the economy, the sectoral distribution of employment and the structural transformation influence women's labour market opportunities. This is a demand-side perspective. Women are willing and able to work, but their participation will depend on the availability of suitable jobs. Bidisha et al. (2022) show that women remain disproportionately concentrated in the low-productivity agricultural sector. Brauner-Otto, Yang, and Ng (2023), writing on Nepal, find that women have rarely transitioned between wage labour, salaried work, and self-employment. Upward Mobility Limited for those who are already in work. Bangladesh's garment sector is the main driver of rising female participation there. Still, in Indian states, their sample experienced rising education without non-farm employment growth. Education results in higher female labour force participation only when favourable demand-side conditions are present (Chakraborty & Siddiqui, 2024; Deshpande & Singh, 2024). A clear example of this is seen in Bangladesh, where the strategic

expansion of the garment sector was the primary driver of rising female participation, providing the necessary market opportunities for women to utilise their human capital.

Marriage, Fertility and Care Responsibility

Bedamatta and Bordoloi (2024) estimate that 114.6 million young Indian women, 48 per cent of all female youth aged 15–35, were outside the labour market in 2022–23. This participation gap is closely linked with the household life cycle; specifically, marital status and the presence of children act as barriers to women's labour market entry (Gupta, 2023). Amber and Chichaibelu (2023) find that women's workforce participation has an inverted U-shaped pattern with age, and that urban women exhibit an M-shaped curve, temporarily exiting the workforce during the child-rearing years before returning. Mothers of children aged 0 to 5 are less likely to participate than women without children or women with children aged 6 or older; a larger penalty is observed among women without childcare support. Working mothers face a double burden, as they are responsible for high levels of unpaid domestic work regardless of their hours of market work, which reduces their ability to sustain employment (Taş & Ahmed, 2024).

Social and Cultural Norms

Even amid decades of economic growth, social and cultural norms remain a major barrier to gender equality in South Asia. Bussolo et al. (2023) show that there has been almost no significant progress in reducing gender disparities over the past half-century. In certain instances, they have even become more conservative and created a negative relationship with women's economic outcomes. Endow and Dutta (2022), through a mixed-method study of 1,300 households in Jharkhand, find that social norms are the primary determinants of women's workforce participation. Nur and Jabeen (2024) find that the COVID-19 pandemic reinforced pre-existing patriarchal norms regarding women's labour-market re-entry in Dhaka's informal settlements.

Findings

The evidence reviewed here mainly fails to support the feminisation U-hypothesis in South Asian FLFP trends. Both Lahoti and Swaminathan (2016) and Klasen (2019) find no systematic U-shaped relationship between income levels and women's participation in India. The U-shaped relationship between education and FLFP is confirmed across South Asian countries (Gunatilaka, 2013). However, Sri Lanka and Bhutan are exceptions, as Najeeb, Morales, and Lopez-Acevedo (2020) find a J-shaped relationship; employment increases only for tertiary-educated women.

In India, the evidence from Deshpande and Singh (2024) and Klasen and Pieters (2015) shows that demand-side factors are the primary drivers: declining agricultural employment was not offset by female-intensive manufacturing or service employment, resulting in 'jobless growth'. On the other hand, Bangladesh's higher and rising female labour force participation is mainly demand-driven, which has driven the garment sector to create mass female employment (Chakraborty & Siddiqui, 2024). The literature on marriage, fertility, and household structure recognises unpaid care and domestic responsibilities. The norm-focused literature (Bussolo et al., 2023; Amber & Chichaibelu, 2023; Nur & Jabeen, 2024) finds that conservative gender attitudes remain across generations and socioeconomic groups, even as education and income improve. This helps to explain the education paradox documented in Section 3.2: social stigma attached to low-skilled employment prevents secondary-educated women from taking available jobs.

Policy Implications

The evidence reviewed here has several policy implications.

Demand-Side Implications

Women's employment is very sensitive to local labour demand. structural transformation toward capital-intensive services bypasses women. The policy formulation needs to implement targeted industrial policies to generate female-intensive employment. Policymakers in India should expand labour-intensive export manufacturing sectors in which women have a comparative advantage.

Childcare and Care Infrastructure

The motherhood and marriage penalties documented by Gupta (2023), Taş and Ahmed (2024), and Bedamatta and Bordoloi (2024) point to childcare provision as an important, high-priority intervention. Affordable, community-based childcare centres near employment centres, flexible working arrangements, and paid parental leave would solve the care-based constraint on women's labour supply.

Vocational Training

Basic education alone does not improve the women's labour market outcomes. Education policy should focus on quality and relevance, not only enrolment. Kanjilal-Bhaduri and Pastore (2018) and Seneviratne (2019) both suggest that technical and vocational training could close the education-participation gap by providing secondary-educated women with formal employment opportunities.

Norm Change and Social Protection

Community-based awareness programs, media campaigns, and school-level curricula focusing on gender equality. Norm change is a slow process, so the norm-change interventions must be sustained and targeted across socioeconomic groups. Reforms to social protection systems are necessary to formalise and support the work of informal workers, mainly women (Nur and Jabeen, 2024).

Conclusion

The key issue motivating this review is why improvements in education, income, and health have failed to increase female labour force participation in the region. There is no single answer. The evidence shows an interaction among multiple demand-side and supply-side constraints, with varying relative importance across countries and contexts. Economic growth is not a reliable driver of female participation; the composition of growth is more important than its rate. The U-shaped relationship between education and female labour force participation is strong across South Asian contexts. Women largely bear Unpaid care responsibilities, which limit their labour supply, and this can be solved by expanding childcare services. Social norms are persistent and independent constraints that are not automatically resolved by rising incomes or education.

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